

Victim's Approaches to Repairing SMEs Interorganisational Trust in Weak Institutional Environments

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Abstract

Trust building plays a key role in transforming organisations, yet many small and medium enterprises (SMEs) struggle to develop and sustain trust due to limited resources and expertise. This challenge is particularly pronounced when it comes to repairing trust after violations, which can threaten the very survival of these enterprises. This article examines the approaches victims take to repair interorganisational trust in weak institutional environments. Using embeddedness theory, the study explores how trust relations are shaped by institutional contexts and social networks. Based on empirical data from 24 cases of internationally trading Ghanaian SMEs, the research develops a model illustrating how entrepreneurs and smaller businesses initiate trust repair following violations. The findings reveal that in weak institutional contexts, SMEs are more proactive in initiating and repairing trust compared to the perpetrators of trust violations. This study significantly contributes to the literature on trust repair by providing a deeper understanding of these processes in developing economies.

Keywords: *SMEs, Trust repair, Interorganisational trust, Embeddedness theory, Institutional contexts, Developing economies*

Introduction

In the last three decades or so, the growing importance of trust building in organizations and effects of trust violation (Pozner, 2008; Williams, 2007; Omeihe, 2019; 2023; Svare et al., 2020) has fostered a growing body of scholarly works on the subject in a host of contexts (e.g., Gillespie & Dietz, 2009; Poppo, Zhou & Li, 2015; Yang et al., 2019). Although many studies recognize trust as an essential component for organizations seeking success in today's uncertain global environment (Poppo et al., 2015; Gillespie, 2017), building trust remains a major obstacle confronting new ventures who often lack the resources or expertise to develop and nurture trust with multiple stakeholders. This is more so in the cases of repairing trust after trust violations, which can precipitate the collapse of such enterprises.

In spite of the growing body of research on trust building and repair (Gillespie & Dietz, 2009; Bachmann, Gillespie and Priem, 2015), there remains a dearth of research on how small and medium enterprises (SMEs) recover from trust violations to repair and restore past relationships. This is a particular issue in the context of emerging markets, where SMEs make up the majority of the firms whilst they also rely on personal ties to develop and maintain relationships with important stakeholders (Peng, 2017; Peng & Luo, 2000). In addition, in such contexts firm often rely on trust to underpin their operation due to weak formal institutions and weaker legal systems (Amankwah-Amoah Chen et al., 2019). Nevertheless, there is a lack of understanding of how SMEs that fall victim to trust violations repair trust (Amoako, 2018).

This article seeks to address these major deficiencies in the current literature by examining the processes of trust repairs after breaches in SMEs' relationships in an emerging country context. Taking the lens of embeddedness theory, this article is able to explore how trust relations are embedded in institutional contexts and existing social relations that shape networks (Granovetter, 1985).

Internationally trading entrepreneurs and their SMEs in Ghana were chosen as the empirical setting. In Ghana, like many emerging economies, the formal institutional structures are weak with limited use of legally binding commercial contracts (Amankwah-Amoah & Debrah, 2010; Amoakoa & Lyon, 2014; Lin & Wang, 2008) and support from state-backed institutions is also limited. The internationally trading SME sector is particularly interesting for the study of trust repairs given that partners tend to come from different cultures (Pearce, 2001) and possess multiple cultural identities, which make cross-cultural trust building and maintenance

challenging (Saunders et al., 2010). The present research offers several contributions to trust violation and repair literature in the international context. First, in spite of growing streams of research on trust (Gillespie & Dietz, 2009), there remains limited research attention to processes of trust repair after violation in SMEs (Wright & Eternad, 2001). By integrating insights of trust violation and trust repair literatures (Fallon et al., 2017; Gillespie & Dietz, 2009), we offer a more in-depth analysis of the precise processes of repairing and rebuilding trust after violation by SMEs in an uncertain institutional environment. In so doing, our study adds specificity as to the integrative mechanisms of how small firms building trust after violation.

Our study contributes to the literature on trust repair (Fallon et al., 2017; Gillespie & Dietz, 2009) by developing a model that demonstrates how entrepreneurs and smaller businesses in developing economies, who fall victim of trust violations, often initiate trust repair. We also deepen our understanding of trust repair process by articulating that SMEs that fall victim to trust violations in such contexts of weak institutions initiate and repair trust more than the perpetrators of trust violations. The rest of the article is organised as follows. In the next section, we review the literature on trust violation and repair. We then present an analysis of the research methodology. Following this, the findings from the article are presented. The implications for theory and practice are then examined.

Trust Repair After Violations

We focus specifically on literature on trust and institution-based views (Peng, 2014). There is no consensus on the exact definition of trust (Pirson et al., 2019). In this paper, we define it as “a psychological state comprising the intention to accept vulnerability based upon positive expectations of the intentions or behaviour of another” (Rousseau et al., 1998, p. 395), or “a set of expectations shared by all those involved in an exchange” (Zucker, 1986, p.54). Personal trust draws on relationships between individuals based on prior and ongoing interaction, and institutional-based trust allows relationships to develop based on expectations that legal measures and norms are upheld by all parties (Zucker, 1986). Institutions are broadly conceptualized to refer to the “rules of the game” in a society, based on formal institutions such as regulations, laws and rules, and informal institutions such as norms, cultures and ethics (North, 1990, p.3; Scott, 1995). These can provide the backdrop for individuals to build trust and forge stronger relationships (Peng, 2014; Fuglsang, 2015; Zucker, 1986). We build on the large body of trust literature that makes a distinction between personal and organizational-level trust (Schilke & Cook, 2013; Kroeger, 2011), with this paper focusing on the former. While there can be trust between organizations, in this study we wanted to explore how trust is repaired by

entrepreneurs owning SMEs (or by senior managers), based on their personal relationships (Amoako & Lyon 2014). Individual-level trust is particularly evident amongst SMEs in Ghana where entrepreneurs owning and managing smaller businesses remain key decision makers and key boundary spanners for their organisations (Kuada & Thomsen, 2005; Amoako & Matlay, 2015). The seminal work on trust by Schoorman, Mayer and Davis (2007:346) draws on a long tradition of organizational research showing that “trust of either the dominant coalition or the management team is critical to understanding organisational trust, since it is this level of trust that will govern the strategic actions of the organisation”. We recognize that individual trust can become “part of the fabric of organizational action” (Schilke & Cook, 2013) as relationships unfold and organizations grow.

Formal institutions impact on trustworthy behavior and perceived trust violations due to the incentives and sanctions that can be imposed on partners. Regarding informal institutions, the degree of uncertainty is found where there is greater divergence on cultural backgrounds (Altinay et al., 2014; Omeihe et al., 2021). Past studies have shown that trust violations originate from information that differs from a trustor’s expectations of the behavior of the trustees (Lewicki, 2014; Kim et al., 2004). Yet, the possibility of violations of trust are inherent and may be unavoidable in any trusting relationship (Skinner et al., 2014).

Trust violations may lead to a deterioration of trust and those who become victim may find themselves in a situation that threatens their existence (Bell et al., 2002; Bachmann, 2001). Given that trust in interorganizational relationships is very critical to smaller businesses due to resource constraints, the core challenge following the violation of trust is finding ways to repair the damage. By trust-repair effort, we are referring to the “activities directed at making a trustor’s trusting beliefs and trusting intentions more positive after a violation is perceived to have occurred” (Kim et al., 2004, p.105). Tomlinson and Mayer (2009) emphasized the importance of understanding how damage to trustworthiness is less when the violated party perceive that the other party had less control over their circumstances. Perceptions of trust violations are also shaped by power based on the resources available to each partner in the relationship (Amoako, 2018). In this article, power refers to the ability or capacity or potential to influence, to determine or control the behaviors, intentions, decisions or actions of others in the pursuit of one’s own goals or interest despite resistance (Furubotn & Pejovich, 1972).

A growing body of research has demonstrated that repairing trust may take time due to the need for parties involved to re-establish the reliability and dependability of the perpetrator over a period of time (Lewicki, 2014). Trust repair is shown to involve reinstating trustworthiness

(Gillespie & Dietz, 2009) and changing the perceptions held by the violated party regarding the systems, processes, culture and management practices of an organization (Dirks et al., 2009). At the interpersonal level, current studies mostly suggest that trust repair after violations should originate from the perpetrator. For example, Lewicki and Bunker (1996) suggest that to repair trust, perpetrators must: 1) acknowledge that a violation has occurred, 2) determine the causes of the violation and admit culpability, 3) admit that the violation was destructive and 4) accept responsibility. Thus it is assumed that the victim plays a passive role but recent models recognize that trust repair is interactive with the trustor's actions (Kim et al., 2009) and victim's cognitions of repentance of the perpetrator (Dirks et al., 2011), and yet there is very little knowledge on the role of the victim in trust repair (Amoako, 2018).

Trust repair at organisational level is often more complicated than at personal level. In organizational contexts, Gillespie and Dietz (2009) argue that the target for trust repair may be individuals or groups of individuals that make up an organization. Larger organizations that have violated trust with key stakeholders based on scandals and corruption may be able to repair trust by tightening organizational rules and processes (Erberl et al., 2015; Gillespie & Dietz, 2009). Yet, trust repair at the organizational level creates a further degree of uncertainty and may be more difficult due to the multiplicity of organizational membership and the need for individuals to change their views towards the violating organisation. However, trust repair in SMEs may differ as entrepreneurs of small businesses remain the origin and object of trust (Inkpen & Currall, 1997; Omeihe et al., 2021), and hence play a pivotal role in trust development and repair in SMEs' interfirm relationships based on their strategic decisions. Therefore, in this study we focus on the issue of trust repair at the individual personal level, while drawing implications for research on organizational trust. In spite of these important insights, the repairing of trust and restoration of relationships after trust violations is shaped by context and particularly institutions, thus the courts, cultural expectations and social norms and power play an important role (Ren & Gray, 2009; Hargie et al., 2010; Amoako, 2018). Yet, although power is inherent in all business relationships, in weak institutional contexts it becomes more important in SMEs' relationships particularly when the exchange partner is a larger firm with more resources leading to asymmetric trust (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978; Zaheer & Harris, 2006; Amoako, 2018). Asymmetric trust increases the vulnerability of SMEs in interorganizational relationships and influences interpretations of trust violations and trust-repair processes (Amoako, 2018; Omeihe, 2022). However, there is a dearth of research on how power shapes trust-repair processes within SMEs' interorganisational contexts and particularly in developing economies, and this article aims to address this gap.

SMEs' Trust Repair and Less Formalized Institutions

The present article focuses on entrepreneurs owning and managing SMEs in Africa and offers an interesting context for the study of trust repairs in uncertain institutional environments. Despite the institutional constraints, successful international trading occurs as entrepreneurs draw on trust in alternative institutions and norms (Amoako & Matlay, 2015; Omeihe, 2019; 2023). Economic activity often depends on less formal institutions such as trade associations that help to reduce transaction costs through the provision of information on market prices, reputation, price negotiations and contract enforcement. These may be found to be operating in parallel to legal systems to help ensure contracts are upheld and trust violations and disputes settled, drawing on association and industry/sector norms (Amoako & Lyon, 2014; Amoako, et al., 2018). For example, entrepreneurs owning Ghanaian internationally trading SMEs rely on trade associations, religious bodies, personal networks such as family/kinship and friendships to repair trust. Similar relationships are found across Africa (Fadahunsi & Rosa, 2002; Ghauri et al., 2003; Amoako, 2018; Omeihe, 2023) and in other emerging economies such as China (Lin & Wang, 2008; Tsui-Auch & Mollering, 2010; Muethel & Hoegl, 2012). This may differ in other contexts and particularly in larger organizations and for smaller organizations operating in contexts where formal institutions are strong and yet these differences are rarely captured by current models on trust repair. We summarise the current literature on trust-repair processes in an emerging economy context by developing a holistic framework (Figure 1) that conceptualizes SMEs' entrepreneurial trust-repair processes in weak institutions. Figure 1 shows that when the entrepreneur's initial trust is perceived to be violated, the perpetrator initiates trust repair at the personal and organizational levels through the following steps: 1) acknowledge violations, 2) determine causes and admit culpability, 3) admit violation was destructive, 4) accept responsibility, 5) tighten organizational rules, 6) review organizational processes and 7) change attitudes of members of victim organization. It shows further that trust repairs are shaped by weak formal institutions, cultural institutions and personalized networks with customers, suppliers and facilitators and power relations in networks. While this conceptual model presents a more holistic view of trust repair in SMEs' interorganisational relationships in an emerging-economy context, there is still very little understanding of the role of the victim in trust repair in SMEs' relationships (Amoako, 2018). The empirical study helps to address this gap by examining the roles of the victim and perpetrator in SMEs' entrepreneurial trust repairs.

Method

Research setting

The case of entrepreneurs and SMEs engaged in international trading from Ghana provides a lens for examining trust repair when there is uncertainty in terms of operating with weak legal institutions, with relationships that cross-cultural boundaries and with small businesses that may have less control over their operating environment. Ghana is deemed a suitable case study context as SMEs are the largest part of the Ghanaian economy, representing about 70 percent of GDP (ITC, 2016; Appiah-Adu, Okpattah & Amoako, 2018). Indeed, over 90 percent of exports outside of the traditional export sectors of cocoa, gold and oil are undertaken by SMEs (GEPA, 2014). Despite the international economic shocks and recessions, international trading continues to expand rapidly in Ghana with exporting recording significant gains between 2010 and 2015 (ITC, 2016). However, businesses in Ghana face a degree of uncertainty, characterized by formal institutional structures that are weak with limited use of legally binding commercial contracts. Entrepreneurs of internationally trading SMEs perceive the legal system to have excessive delays and high costs (Amoako & Lyon, 2014; Amoako, 2018).

Accordingly, many smaller firms face difficulties in enforcing contracts particularly related to cross-border trade. Hence, entrepreneurs and their SMEs rely more on trust-based networks due to the institutional deficiencies within the nation. Trust research has achieved a certain level of maturity and so we adopted an abductive approach in order to refine and extend knowledge using the literature and empirical data from 24 cases of internationally trading SMEs in Ghana. Abductive reasoning combines both inductive and deductive strategies to research and involves a constant moving from the empirical to theoretical dimensions of the analysis (Strauss & Corbin, 1990).

Abductive reasoning describes the process of theoretical reflection that results from unmet empirical expectations backwards in order to invent a plausible world or theory that would make the surprise meaningful (Van Maanen et al., 2007; Omeihe & Harrison, 2024). In this study, the literature review identified the emphasis on perpetrator-led trust repair. The subsequent data collection, taking a more inductive approach, provided surprising evidence of victim-led approaches to trust repair, and repair strategies that are embedded in the existing context. The qualitative approach was used to enable the researchers to understand how the social world looks from the perspective of entrepreneurs being studied (Sullivan, 2001). The approach helped to unearth processes that may be essential for repairing trust in relationships but may remain hidden in large-scale surveys (Yin, 2009).

Figure 1. Trust repairs in SMEs' interorganizational relationships in weak institutional environments

Case Study Selection and Data Collection

The selection of the case organisations was based on purposive and theoretical sampling in accordance with the research questions and the theoretical framework (Marshall & Rossman, 1999). We selected multiple cases based on the novelty of the Ghanaian context with regard to trust research and also to ensure important sources of contextual variation to facilitate capturing comparisons (Yin, 2009) in trust repair in terms of market location and industry. Firstly, the sample was stratified to have 12 cases each from export markets in West Africa and intercontinental (outside Africa) markets due to the potential differences in entrepreneurs' perceptions and experiences of trust-based networks within the two markets (Guest et al., 2006). Secondly, the sample was selected to represent an equal coverage of businesses in three contrasting industries (agriculture production and marketing, manufacturing and services) exporting to the West African or intercontinental markets. These sectors play a major role in the Ghanaian economy (Robson et al., 2009). Since there is no single register for small firms in Ghana (Robson & Freel, 2008), a sample frame was developed through identifying businesses attending export fairs, membership of trade associations and the limited lists of businesses held by support organizations including The Ghana Export Promotion Authority, Ghana Chamber of Commerce, National Board of Small-scale Businesses, and Association of Ghana Industries). Businesses that were not on these lists were also identified through interviews with key informants such as trade-association leaders in the informal export sector mostly based in Accra, Kumasi and Techiman open markets. A snowballing approach of asking businesses to identify other businesses was also used.

In all, 148 exporting firms were identified and 40 of them were selected using four filter questions based on firms employing fewer than 100 people, selling products or services to West Africa or intercontinental markets, operating in agriculture, manufacturing and services sectors and not less than two years old. The initial invitation to participate was rejected by 25 entrepreneurs, citing lack of time and interest as the main concerns. Of the 40 selected, a further purposeful selection process was used to select 24 case studies. While gender and ethnicity were not key selection criteria, the sample is well balanced. The cases are focused on the main trading centers of Accra, Kumasi and Techiman. Table 1 demonstrates the main characteristics of the 24 cases.

In line with the abductive approach, we collected data through three key sources: (1) literature review, 2) semi-structured interviews and (3) observations. We employed in-depth and repeated semi-structured interviews with entrepreneurs and managers in 24 internationally trading SMEs in Ghana over a two-year period after reviewing the literature. Semi-structured interviews were carried out with 19 entrepreneurs and five managers who deputized for their entrepreneurs. The interviews took place in their workplace and on a few occasions in their homes, with the choice of location depending on where the interviewees felt most comfortable. Open-ended questions drawn from an interview guide were used during the conversations to allow the use of a critical incident technique to investigate how owners/managers reacted to specific incidents that had happened (Flanagan, 1954).

The critical incident technique enabled the researcher to probe deeper into events in order to unearth the dynamic nature of trust and capture the very critical subjective meanings that were essential elements of understanding entrepreneurs' behavior (Sullivan, 2001; Marshall & Rossman, 1999). The questions asked at the initial stages of the interviews were descriptive to allow the conversation to be initiated. Hence, direct questions on trust violations and repairs were not used in order not to limit access to sensitive information and also to avert the misinterpretation of the concepts in different contexts (Lyon, 2012). Latter questions related to the respondents' relationships and specific incidents of threats to these relationships, why and how entrepreneurs repaired trust, and the types of contextual influences that shaped their decisions. In a further round of interviews after the first phase of analysis, more information was requested on the processes of repairing and rebuilding relationships after violations of trust. Questions on respondents' profiles such as age, ethnicity and education levels were the last to be asked as interviewees considered them to be "sensitive".

To explore the approaches of trust repair, interviewees were asked to discuss a single important incident where they "did business with a partner after there had been a problem between you". Examples were given by all 24 interviewees of SME cases. The analysis of cases revealed that trust-repair efforts were influenced by norms of family/kinship, religion, trade associations, the nature of product/service and asymmetric power relations. This could be explained given that exporters' perceptions of trust violation to a greater extent determined the repair mechanisms they deployed. The interviewees in this article were more willing to discuss those examples where they had been the victim. Due to the sensitive nature of trust violations and issues of

ethics of research and logistics of researching exporting enterprises, the researcher was not able to discuss some issues with both parties of a trust-based relationship. Eight of the interviews were undertaken in Twi (the most widely spoken language in Ghana) with others in English (the official language across the country). Interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed into English; this approach facilitated gaining insights into meanings of SME owners/managers.

The interview data were enriched and validated through the use of observations of meetings, seminars and trade fairs. Data were also collected at ports and markets in order to observe interactions. Formal meetings were conducted in English, while informal interaction and observation required knowledge of both Twi and English. Participation in these arenas of observation and gaining access to interviewees was enabled through drawing on an acceptance of the researcher due to common culture and the previous experience in participating in export trading of different kinds in the past.

Data Analysis and Theory Building

An interpretive approach was used to analyze data on trust repair in order to provide a more in-depth understanding of the processes of trust repair (Miles & Huberman, 1994; Yin, 2009).

We transcribed and manually analyzed the data first by developing codes. The codes were identified through the analysis of the data and the literature was interrogated in order to find out how the theoretical framework explained the data. Through cross-case analysis, the first-order concepts were identified based on the key terms and phrases across all 24 cases. The initial codes identified for this article are: trust violations, trust-repair types, perpetrator, victim, repair tactics, power relations and repair outcomes. The second phase of coding involved scrutinizing data and coding the processes of violation and repair according to the roles of the victim, perpetrator, institutions and power. The analysis was then followed by more data collection and then further analysis. In this way, data collection and data analysis were iterative with the researcher going back and forth between the initial framework, data sources and analysis in order to generate new theory (Strauss & Corbin, 1990). The literature on trust repair was then used as previously discussed to understand the role of the victim, the perpetrator, institutions and power relations, and how these reflect the evidence in the interviews. In a third phase of the analysis, we were able to identify common themes of trust violations and trust-repair strategies and identify institutions and power-related themes and outcomes of trust repair.

Results

Trust Building with Less Formal Institutions

The data analysis indicates that internationally trading SMEs use different types of relationships that are built on trust. These interorganisational relationships were based on reciprocity and mutuality both between organizations and between individuals in each organization. There is no single word for trust in Twi, the most common language in Ghana. Trust is expressed as a belief or a faith. Interviewees also referred to relationships where they were either reliant on or supporting others. An exporter of pineapples to intercontinental markets expressed how he used trust with his key supplier: “What I mean is we talk and work as a family, we lean on each other because he needs me and I need him” (Case 19). All 24 SMEs had built trust in relationships with customers, suppliers and trade associations that allowed them to overcome the many challenges that beset cross-cultural exchanges, the uncertain formal institutions and the “psychic distance”. A distinction can be drawn between the cross-cultural relationships with West African partners where there is evidence of common norms related to doing business and social relationships (Amoako et al., 2018; Amoako & Matlay, 2015), and those in intercontinental relationships outside of Africa.

For example, the relationships within the region could draw on common practices related to socializing with business partners, with interviewees referring to attending weddings and funerals. There are a range of traditional institutions and norms that are both the basis of personal or organizational trust and can be seen as forms of institutional trust in themselves. Most explicit is the legal system that is perceived as imperfect but allows organizations to assume some of the risk in a relationship. In each case there are culturally specific norms and references to indigenous institutions showing how relationships are embedded in existing social structures. For example, agricultural produce exporters to the West African markets referred to specialized agents located in foreign countries. Respondents referred to these commission agents (*Efiewuranom*) in Nigeria, Burkina Faso, Niger and Mali. They served to shrink the psychic distance using personalized trust reinforced through common religious beliefs and languages, the sharing of information and, at times, the provision of accommodation in distant markets (Amoako & Lyon, 2014).

Other institutional forms found in both Ghana and markets across Africa are trade associations. These can be conceptualized as forms of institutional-based trust with these less formal institutions operating in parallel to the state.

Table 1. *Details of Firms and respondents*

Case	Founded	Employees	Activity	Sector	Markets	Interviewee	Location
1	1998	5	Exporter of African beads	Service	West Africa	Owner/manager	Greater Accra
2	2003	12	Servicing of diesel pumps	Service	West Africa	Owner/manager	Ashanti
3	1989	6	Hotel	Service	West Africa	Manager	Brong Ahafo
4	2009	17	Retailer of petroleum products	Service	West Africa	Manager	Ashanti
5	1983	6	Exporter of cola nuts	Agriculture	West Africa	Owner/manager	Ashanti
6	1990	10	Exporter of maize	Agriculture	West Africa	Owner/manager	Brong Ahafo
7	2001	35	Fresh eggs	Agriculture	West Africa	Owner/manager	Brong Ahafo
8	1985	10	Fresh oranges	Agriculture	West Africa	Owner/manager	Brong Ahafo
9	2004	8	Fashion designer	Manufacturing	West Africa	Owner/manager	Greater Accra
10	1995	13	Fashion designer	Manufacturing	West Africa	Owner/manager	Greater Accra
11	2000	10	Manufacturer of cocoa powder	Manufacturing	West Africa	Owner/manager	Greater Accra
12	1969	15	Exporter of Jewellery	Manufacturing	West Africa	Manager	Ashanti
13	2008	37	Hotel and conference facilities	Service	USA, UK, EU	Manager	Ashanti
14	2000	12	Hotel	Service	USA, EU	Owner/Manager	Ashanti
15	1996	9	Export of Kente cloth	Service	USA, UK	Owner/manager	Ashanti
16	1995	15	Hotel	Service	USA, EU	Manager	Brong Ahafo
17	2003	26	Exporter of fresh vegetables	Agriculture	UK	Owner/manager	Greater Accra
18	2002	38	Exporter of fresh cashew nuts	Agriculture	India, Europe	Owner/manager	Greater Accra
19	1998	60	Exporter of fresh pineapples	Agriculture	EU, Asia	Owner/manager	Central
20	2002	20	Exporter of fresh shea butter	Agriculture	EU, USA	Owner/manager	Eastern
21	1991	38	Processor/Exporter of spices	Manufacturing	USA	Owner/manager	Greater Accra
22	1986	25	Manufacturer of beads	Manufacturing	Canada, USA	Owner/manager	Greater Accra
23	2003	25	Processing of shea butter	Manufacturing	USA	Owner/manager	Northern
24	1996	20	Drying and processing of fruits	Manufacturing	Europe, China	Owner/manager	Greater Accra

The trade associations play a crucial role in facilitating exporting through linking organizations and settling disputes. They also lobbied on behalf of members, provided business information, organized trade fairs, facilitated networking and provided training to members.

Not surprisingly most exporters regarded membership in these associations as crucial for their exporting competitiveness (Amoako et al., 2018). A trader in fresh oranges selling through an efiewura (agent) in Mali stated: “The efiewura (agent) who belong to trade associations are registered and it is those who are trusted that are registered” (Case 8). Relationships are therefore based on institutions that can be the basis of trust themselves, or which underpin organizational or personal trust. Threats to these relationships come when trust is perceived to be violated.

Victim-led and Perpetrator-led Approaches to Trust Repair

Our findings indicate that not all entrepreneurs studied adopted the same approach with regard to trust repair. A summary of the cases is presented in Table 2. While much previous research has focused on the role of the perpetrator wanting to rebuild trust (e.g. Lewicki & Bunker, 1996; Kim et al., 2009), analysis of the cases surprisingly showed that trust repair was mostly initiated by the victim, as only a quarter of respondents (six of 24) reported a perpetrator-led approach to trust repair. Perpetrator-led trust repair is illustrated by a hotel manager who hosts customers from USA and the EU who waited until a partner who caused the violation to her initiated the repair process:

“They supplied poor-quality products to us and I did not buy from them for some time and I did not contact them but later the manager called to apologize and so we are now buying from them.”
(Case 14)

Surprisingly, the cross-case analysis showed that three-quarters of case studies (18 out of 24) could give examples of trust repair that had been initiated by the victims. However, there were slight differences between the markets with almost all (10 of 12) exporters to West African markets compared to two-thirds (eight of 12) of their colleagues in intercontinental markets who had fallen victim to trust violations proactively repairing trust in their relationships, notably, within relationships characterized by asymmetric power relations. Asymmetric power relations increase the vulnerability of SMEs in interorganizational relationships (Pfeffer & Salancik, 1978; Zaheer & Harris, 2006), and shapes interpretations of trust violations and trust- repair processes (Amoako, 2018). Such proactive, victim-led trust repair was more likely to be used by organizations dealing with perishable produce and hence having limited market power and a

degree of dependency on their customers. The case of an entrepreneur exporting fresh pineapples to Europe and Asia shows how such unequal power relations forced weaker partners to renew the relationship and look for ways to trust the other party despite being the victim:

“I get a problem with delayed remittances but I contact them on such occasions. It’s business, and sometimes you give in, other times you insist it’s mutual.” (Case 19)

These findings are contrary to existing assumptions in the literature that regard the perpetrator as the initiator of trust repairs (e.g. Kim et al., 2009; Dirks et al., 2011; Gillespie & Dietz, 2009) while paying very little attention to the role of the victim in trust repair.

It became evident that entrepreneurs of SMEs who had fallen victim to trust violations recognized that trust repair was an integral part of their overall business interests and hence did not always wait for perpetrators to initiate the repair process; they did it themselves.

The data further suggest that trust repair can be an instantaneous or instinctive process occurring habitually. This non-calculative or routinized action is shaped by both existing norms (such as those related to kinship or religion) and shaped by power relations. Case 3 illustrates this approach in these words: “You know in my business I always pray, and you know in the Bible we believe that God asks us to forgive and since He is in control I just accept the situation and I forgave.” (Case 3)

A statement from Case 5 also shows that in the cola-nut industry it is the norm not to leave your long-term customer when he defaults on payments, in fact to do otherwise suggested that the exporter has “run away” which indicated abandonment.

“You know in this cola business so far as you have worked with the fellow for a very long time, you can’t run away and leave him because he cannot pay your money.” (Case 5)

Those parties with less power are more likely to consider “acceptance and forgiveness” and immediately look to repair the relationship. For example, entrepreneurs exporting agricultural products were observed to interpret trust violations by referring to the nature of their products. Case 7 who exports fresh eggs to Niger explained how he perceived trust violations in this way:

“As you may know, it is not easy to keep eggs in this country so we don’t sack our customers when they default but we try to encourage them to pay us in instalments as we continue to supply them.” (Case 7)

Table 2. *Trust violations and trust repair tactics in SMEs' interorganizational relationships in weak institutional environments*

Case	Nature of trust violations	Trust repair approach used	Trust repair tactics	Outcome
1	Default of payment	Victim-led	Requested an explanation.	Flimsy explanation offered and trust destroyed
2	Supplier sent poor quality spare parts	Perpetrator -led	Supplier offered flimsy explanation.	Trust was destroyed
3	Default of payment	Victim-led	Requested for an explanation	Credible explanation and money paid back; trust repaired
4	Default of payment	Perpetrator-led	Customer offered an explanation and apology.	Customer paid back; trust repaired
5	Default of payment	Victim-led	Used trade association leaders as intermediaries	Apology offered, money paid in instalments and trust repaired
6	Supplier sent lesser quantity of goods.	Victim-led	Used leaders of association (intermediaries)	Credible explanation offered, goods refunded, trust repaired
7	Supplier diverted credit to other uses.	Victim-led	Asked for explanation and an apology	Goods supplied in instalments.and trust repaired
8	Customer reduced the agreed price of goods	Victim-led	Used leaders of association as intermediaries	Amount refunded and trust repaired
9	Defaulted payment due to bereavement	Victim-led	Asked for an explanation	Credible explanation offered and trust repaired
10	Delayed time for payments	Victim-led	Complained to defaulters' mother	Debt paid and trust partially repaired as credit was reduced
11	Bank delayed time for transferring payments	Victim-led	Prayed and asked for pastor and divine intervention.	Debt paid and trust repaired
12	Customer disappeared after receiving goods on credit.	Victim-led	Customer threatened to use local gods to curse perpetrator	Debt partly paid but trust destroyed
13	Supplier supplied lesser quantity of the goods.	Victim-led	Asked for an explanation	Received credible explanation and trust repaired
14	Supplier sent poor quality products.	Perpetrator-led	Offered an apology through victim's brother).	Trust repaired
15	Supplier delayed the goods	Victim-led	Used church and community leaders to mediate	Credible explanation offered and trust repaired
16	Customer delayed payment.	Perpetrator-led	Offered an apology and an explanation	Trust repaired
17	Association leaders used dubious accounting record keeping.	Victim-led	Asked for an explanation.	Leaders explained and apologised and trust repaired
18	Court allegedly brought forward case without notice	Victim-led	Asked for an explanation.	Court clerk lied and trust in court system destroyed.
19	Customers delayed payment	Victim-led	Asked for explanation.	Apology offered and trust repaired
20	Suppliers delayed goods	Victim-led	Asked for an explanation	Flimsy explanation offered and trust destroyed
21	Supplier supplied junk machinery	Victim-led	Used Ghana embassy staff as intermediaries	Money not received and trust destroyed
22	Customer did not pay for goods on time	Perpetrator-led	Offered explanation and an apology	Trust repaired
23	Supplier missed out on date of supply.	Perpetrator-led	Offered an explanation	Trust repaired
24	Main customer breached agreement	Victim-led	Asked for an explanation.	Customer lied but trust repaired.

Evidence of such approaches was observed where the violation is not explicitly stated or where repair of trust has taken place while the victim of trust violation is not willing to refer to the breaking of expectations as a loss of trust. This continuation of a relationship can be either a repair of trust or simply a suspension of distrust. To sum up, the findings of this study show that in weak institutional contexts, entrepreneurs and smaller businesses that are victims of trust violations in SMEs' interorganizational relationships often initiate and repair trust due to the interplay of weak legal/court and support institutions, norms of cultural institutions, nature of networks and personalized relationships and power relations, and yet the current literature pays less attention to these context-based factors and instead highlights that perpetrators initiate trust repair. These findings have been used to develop a novel framework that depicts the factors that influence perpetrator-led and victim-led trust-repair approaches. Figure 2 shows that SMEs entrepreneurial trust-repair processes in weak institutions can be initiated by either the victim or the perpetrator depending on a number of factors. Victim-led repairs occur when the entrepreneurs and SMEs refrain from relying on the weak legal/court systems due to perceived corruption, high costs and long processes, and instead draw on cultural institutions and networks of family/kinship, friendship, religion and trade associations to repair trust. Furthermore, entrepreneurs embark on victim-led trust repair when they realize that the perishability of their product/service, switching costs and the nature of resources available are more in a particular relationship. On the contrary, when these factors are less, they may wait for the perpetrator to initiate the trust-repair process, thus showing how power shapes trust repair. Table 3 explains these two approaches in more detail.

Trust-repair Tactics

In the context of institutional weaknesses and lack of legal measures, there is a greater reliance on the rebuilding of personalized relationships. The analysis of case studies showed three trust-repair tactics were used once the rebuilding process had started: 1) offering an explanation, 2) offering an apology, and 3) using intermediaries. It is important to state that these three repair tactics were not mutually exclusive as, for example, explanations were often complemented by an apology.

Figure 2. *Factors shaping victim-led and perpetrator-led trust repairs in SMEs' interorganizational relationships*

Furthermore, intermediaries tend to demand explanations when settling disputes and the victim may have to offer an apology to the victim (Amoako, 2018). Explanations are key to trust repair (see Gillespie, 2017). In perpetrator-led approaches, the perpetrators offered explanations in the processes of repairing trust. The processor and exporter of shea butter to the USA stated:

“They missed out on the date for supply and they sent me an e-mail afterwards explaining why; they also wanted to know what to do but I did not get back to them until after some time, but now we are working together again.” (Case 23)

This article shows that explanations do not need to necessarily come from the perpetrator as espoused by the current literature (e.g. Lewicki & Bunker, 1996; Dirks et al., 2011; Gillespie, 2017; Omeihe, 2023). In the case of victim-led approaches, explanations were provided only after they had been requested by the victim. Notably, explanations acknowledging trust violations were found to facilitate the repair process since it demonstrated that the perpetrator was honest and empathetic towards the victim. While some perpetrators acknowledged faults, others used the explanation to deny culpability. In both West African and intercontinental markets, trust violators who denied culpability at times offered “tangible” reasons as to why the

expectation was not met. For example, one case explained that their partners attributed trust violations to delays by the banks in transferring payments to them (Case 11). These explanations are widely accepted by victims of trust violations who recognize the challenges of working in an uncertain institutional environment. Explanations could also relate to specific cultural norms such as the loss of a family member. An entrepreneur (fashion designer) exporting textiles to West African markets explained why she cooperated again with a partner who had been bereaved:

“Unfortunately, the woman has just been widowed and has not been working for the past three months so I don’t want to bother her and that is why I continue to work with her and even give her credit.” (Case 9)

Regardless of need for trust, explanations related to socio-cultural norms concerning bereavement are generally accepted in the West African markets. The bereaved might abstain from working for a period ranging from days to months depending on the relationship to the person who died. However, such explanations were found to be less tenable in intercontinental relationships where there may be less acceptance of such norms – evidence of the greater psychic distance compared to building relationships in other countries particularly outside Africa. Nevertheless, most of the entrepreneurs indicated that they would only abandon their businesses for a few weeks after bereavement.

The use of explanations and demonstrating empathy were found to open windows of opportunity for expressing regret and rendering an apology to the victim – the second tactic for repairing trust. Providing an apology by the perpetrator was found to be an effective tactic for repairing trust. Interestingly, the literature (Hargie et al., 2010; Lewicki & Bunker, 1996; Lewicki, 2014) does not emphasize that victims looking to repair trust also seek apologies from perpetrators of trust violations, as shown by the fashion designer exporting from Ghana to West African markets:

“This lady defaulted but I complained to her mother about the incident and she apologized to me and then came to pay the money. She continues to buy from me only that I have reduced the amount of credit.” (Case 10)

The third tactic found was the use of intermediaries. These may be individuals known to each party or trade associations who can play conflict-resolution roles parallel to the courts (Amoako & Lyon, 2014). These intermediaries could influence either party to give in to the demands of the other. A third (eight of 24) of the entrepreneurs in all three sectors stated that they relied on

intermediaries in repairing trust with their partners. This practice was found to be more common in domestic and West African markets than in intercontinental markets (one of eight) due to the range of indigenous institutions and facilitators that play roles in conflict resolution. An exporter of maize to West African markets regarded the use of intermediaries as more cost effective than going to court:

“I preferred to sit down with the person and sort it out. I chose to exhaust other avenues because going to court is expensive and also a waste of time. So, I invited the leaders of the association to help resolve the issue. It is always good to bring in such people because they will bear witness that you had wanted to resolve the issue peacefully.” (Case 6)

The approaches of these intermediaries draw on norms of mediation and conflict resolution that can differ between cultures. For example, the trade associations resolved disputes through association leaders who convened hearings during which the norms of the associations were used to settle the dispute. These norms include the means of presenting an argument, the acceptance of the final decision by association leaders and the ability of associations to exclude people from markets and exert power through peer pressure and shaming. The frequent use of intermediaries by organisations in Ghana could be explained given the culturally specific role of *dwanetoafo* (intercessor) who features regularly in traditional dispute-resolution institutions such as chiefs’ courts in Ghana and in the West African region. Intermediaries are crucial in trust repair in both emerging and in advanced economies (see Amoako, 2018; Ritzer-Angerer, 2018). Table 3 shows the trust-repair tactics in more detail.

Outcomes of Trust Violation and Repair

Some of the case organizations were able to restore trust to their original position after taking these steps, as outlined in the previous phase. Overall three-quarters of entrepreneurs indicated that trust was repaired between them and their partners, and as a result the relationships were restored. In all those cases, the perpetrators had offered an explanation and/or an apology or used an intermediary. These repair tactics had been followed up by the payments of the monies involved, promises not to repeat those practices that led to the violations, and steps taken to rectify the problems, for example changing banks as done by Case 11. Nonetheless, one entrepreneur changed the terms of the relationship by reducing the amount of credit offered to a particular partner even though trust was repaired and the relationship restored (see Case 10 in Table 2).

In a quarter of the cases, trust-repair efforts failed because some of the entrepreneurs lost a

contract with a customer due to delays from a supplier while others lost substantial amounts of money. An entrepreneur exporting to the EU and USA explained why he terminated a relationship with a supplier:

“I recall that when I was dealing in handicraft I had a problem with a supplier and as you may be aware export orders are time bound and the supplier could not meet the demand even though I had paid him in advance and it made me lose my customers. So, I decided to stop working with that supplier.” (Case 20)

The above entrepreneur’s decision to terminate the relationship could be understood given that due to global competition exporters are obliged to meet stricter supply deadlines which are often tied to penalties and rewards.

Another entrepreneur who processes spices for export recounted how she lost a considerable amount of money and time due to violations of trust by her partner in the EU:

“I am a living example of another serious consequence of breaches in trust in collaborations. I negotiated for about four years and signed an agreement with my partners in an EU country, yet these partners abroad sent in junk machinery worth US\$100,000. Afterwards, we tried several methods; as you may know this involved a lot of time and money apart from what we had already lost and my company nearly collapsed.” (Case 21)

Table 3. *Trust repair tactics in SMEs' interorganizational relationships in weak institutional environments*

Approach	Explanation	Apology	Intermediary
Victim-led	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Default of payment and a request for an explanation yielded flimsy excuses leading to destruction of trust (Case 1)• Reduction of agreed price by agent in Niger and trade association leaders were requested to intervene and trust repaired (Case 8).• Default of payment by customer due to mourning and trust was repaired (Case 9)• Received lesser quantity of products from supplier but explanations given and trust repaired (Case 13)• Court clerk lied in a case involving credit default and trust destroyed (Case 18)• Delayed order and flimsy explanations given by supplier when asked to explain and so trust not repaired (Case 20).• Main customer in Europe lied, but trust repaired after discussions (Case 24).	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Delayed payments but manager offered an apology and paid and so trust was repaired (Case 3)• Diverting money for supplies to other uses but supplier apologized and trust was repaired (Case 7)• Dubious accounting methods used by association leaders and they apologized after explanation and trust was repaired (Case 17)• Delayed payment but customer apologized and explanation and trust was repaired (Case 19).• Delayed supply of goods but apologized through church and community leaders and trust was repaired (Case 15)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Leaders of association invited by victim to resolve breaches of trust from customer (Case 5; Case 6; Case 8) and trust was repaired• Mother of perpetrator was asked to intervene and trust was repaired (Case 10)• Prayer, religious leaders and divine intervention used and trust was repaired (Case 11)• Curses from local gods invoked as threats leading to perpetrator making part payment of debt but trust not repaired (Case 12).• Embassy staff unable to recover money from supplier of junk machinery and trust not repaired (Case 21)
Perpetrator-led	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Poor quality spare parts received from supplier and flimsy explanations given and so trust was not repaired (Case 2)• Delayed payment for goods but customer offered an explanation followed by an apology and trust was repaired (Case 4)• Delayed supplies but supplier offered credible explanation and trust was repaired (Case 23).	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Delayed payments but customer apologized and trust was repaired (Case 16)• Delayed payments but customer apologized and offered a credible explanation and trust was repaired (Case 22)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Victim's brother asked to intervene through an apology and trust was repaired (Case 14)

Discussion

In the article we sought to contribute to the current literature by focusing on SMEs in emerging economies, shedding light on the tactical approach in identifying and responding to trust violations and repairing trust. The empirical evidence presented is used to show how entrepreneurs owning internationally trading SMEs in Ghana draw on cultural and other institutional norms to adopt suitable repair mechanisms in their business relations with suppliers, customers and export facilitation organizations. The findings indicated that personal trust plays a greater role in organizational trust repair in contexts of uncertainty. Such personalized trust is often linked to norms of reciprocity and friendship, with the mixing of social and business arenas. The norms of family/kinship, friendships and reciprocity, and nature of socializing related to business is culturally specific. The power relations within each relationship are shaped by the market context, the perishable nature of the product/service the resources available in specific relationships and the switching costs involved. The entrepreneurs and SMEs perceived trust to be violated based on breaches of initial trust on payments of goods already supplied, delaying in payments, disappearing after receiving goods on credit and supplying poor-quality products. However, this article makes the distinction between victim-led and perpetrator-led approaches to trust-repair approaches. While the latter approach is emphasized in the literature (such as Lewicki, 2014; Kim et al., 2009), the former approach is given less attention. This study shows that entrepreneurs' trust-repair efforts have tended to avoid the courts and instead relied more on trust in individuals and intermediaries. In circumstances where smaller businesses are dependent on the other party with unequal power, there has been the need for victim entrepreneurs to start the process of repair. This is evidence of considerable asymmetries of power and an example of where a victim has little choice but to invest in trust despite the risks (Bachmann, 2006). This dependency was observed amongst cases in this article as organizations assume away a trust violation. Figure 3 sums up the stages and processes of trust repair in entrepreneurial relationships in weak institutional environments.

Figure 3. Trust repairs in SMEs' interorganizational relationships in weak institutional contexts

Legalistic rules, contracts and sanctions can help repair trust (Gillespie & Dietz, 2009) and as a way of limiting the chance of repetition (Kramer & Lewicki, 2010), but only in contexts with stronger legal institutions and for larger organizations. This article shows that in the context of SMEs, the tactics of trust repair involve rebuilding personalized trust through explanations, seeking apologies and using intermediaries. While existing literature recognizes the role of apologies (e.g. Hargie et al., 2010; Lewicki, 2014), explanations (e.g. Gillespie, 2017) and intermediaries (Ritzer-Angerer, 2018) in trust repair, this article extends our understanding of trust-repair processes by showing why and how entrepreneurs and SMEs who are victims may seek explanations, an apology or use intermediaries in initiating trust repair instead of waiting for perpetrators to initiate the trust-repair process.

In cases where trust repair has failed, the outcomes of trust violations could have varying degrees of negative impact on smaller businesses ranging from deterioration of relationships and loss of resources to near collapse of the businesses (Bell et al., 2002; Bachmann, 2001). The analysis also revealed that in instances when trust was violated, victim entrepreneurs were particularly compelled to spend time to deal with the aftermath of the violations. Time was spent in an attempt to seek redress, repair the relationship, and, if unsuccessful, to build new networks in order to gain access to the vital resources which might have been lost as a result of the violation.

Conclusion

Although considerable recent research attention has been directed towards exploring trust violations and repairs (Fallon et al., 2017), relatively few studies have examined trust-repair processes after violation in SMEs. SMEs play an important role in both domestic and international economic growth (Wright & Eternad, 2001). Thus, our article fills a gap in the current literature by focusing on SMEs in Africa. By examining how actions are embedded in social relations in an African context, this article contributes to the literature on institutions and trust in developing economies (Muethel & Hoegl, 2012; Zaheer & Kamal, 2011). In addition, this research contributes to the literature by providing support for the embeddedness or institutionalist approach to trust that is sensitive to the cultural context and how actions are embedded in social relations (Granovetter, 1985). By examining entrepreneurs and their SMEs operating in uncertain institutional contexts where there is a severe lack of trust in institutions and legal systems, we present frameworks that fill a gap in the literature that has previously focused mostly on studies of larger organizations or individuals that predominantly originate from North America, Europe and Asia.

For SMEs with few employees, we show that individual trust is central but, as organizations grow, trust may also occur at the organizational level as well. There is also a theoretical contribution to understanding trust repair in asymmetric power relations. This shows that trust violation victims are often the initiators of repair where they have less power. These power asymmetries are particularly evident in emerging economies and amongst SMEs.

In the context of smaller businesses in emerging economies, characterized by institutional uncertainty, there is a greater reliance on personalized relationships and the giving of an explanation or apology, as shown by previous studies (Ren & Gray, 2009; Gillespie & Dietz, 2009). However, culturally specific explanations are found that use the concept of institutional uncertainty as a way of denying culpability. This includes references to failures of banking systems for payment of bills or delays in ports. While the legal institutions may not be relied upon, the article found that there is considerable reliance on the use of intermediaries for repairing trust through alternative institutional forms operating in parallel to the courts. These have been reported across the world and particularly in West Africa since the pre-colonial period, particularly with regard to traditional markets in food and agricultural produce (Lyon, 2005). These associations therefore address the power imbalance felt by small businesses across Africa, particularly where they cannot have the same access to the same legal processes as larger firms (Biggs & Shah, 2006).

Limitations and Future Directions

While this article has illuminated how entrepreneurs who own internationally trading SMEs and fall victim to trust violations in interorganizational relationships draw on the culturally specific elements to proactively repair trust in an African context, there are wider implications for understanding the subject in other locations where there is a high degree of institutional uncertainty. This research is limited by its focus on internally trading SMEs from a single country, although this has been necessary for exploring these concepts in depth. Further research is needed to explore these issues elsewhere and examine the culturally specific roles of norms, recognizing that these can vary considerably within countries based on ethnicity, background of key individuals or industry. Future research with a much larger sample could further explore the relationships outlined here. The institutionalist approach demonstrates the importance of understanding the nuances of trust repair in interorganizational relationships in different cultural contexts especially outside of mature market economies where there are less formalized institutional environments and the lack of trust in key institutions such as the judiciary. Longitudinal studies of SMEs will also provide the opportunity to understand trust building,

violation and repair in growing organizations. Such approaches can also examine trust at multiple levels as the individual trust of entrepreneurs becomes part of the fabric of the organizational level trust.

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